

Ovals in a given rectangle. New hypotheses on how Borromini could draw the impost of San Carlino's dome.

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Abstract.

The discovery of mathematical treatises on the problem of inscribing an oval in a rectangle, namely those of Benedetti and Mannheim, has inspired this organised update of the various constructions available and their presumed origins. Their application to the case of Borromini's inscribed oval at San Carlino in Rome, together with new suggestions for practical methods on site, sheds new light on what the artist knew and how he may have worked.

Keywords: Ovals, rectangle, Borromini, Benedetti, Mannheim, San Carlino,

Funding: nA

Conflicts of interest/Competing interests: nA

Introduction

In (Mazzotti, 2014b) the question was raised as to how Francesco Borromini was able to draw an oval within a given rectangle when he had to plan the dome (actually a vault) of the church of San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane in Rome. At the time of its publication and of the subsequent related works (Caputo & Mazzotti, 2019) and (Caputo & Mazzotti, 2025) the oldest known geometric construction was that of Abraham Bosse (Bosse, 1665), whose work was very unlikely to have been known to Borromini, who had been working on the church since 1637.

The author of (Mazzotti, 2014b) argues in his paper that a construction based on the *Connection Locus* (see below) may have been discovered and used by Borromini himself. However, the recent paper (Hotz & Ilchmann, 2024) has shown that a geometric construction was published as early as 1585 by Giovanni Battista Benedetti in Turin (Benedetti, 1585). In addition, it will be shown here how a trial-and-error method may have been used on the building site.

Four-centre ovals

A four-centre (or four-arc) polycentric oval is defined as follows:

A four-centre oval is a closed convex curve with two symmetry axes made of four arcs of circle subsequently smoothly connected; i.e. sharing a common tangent at their connecting point.

See (Mazzotti, 2019) for a monography on the subject of polycentric ovals.

Fig. 1 A four centre oval with all its parameters. Also shown are the tangents at the four connecting points H^* .

Fig. 1 displays an example of a four-centre oval made of arcs with centres K, J, K' and J' . In such an oval the following parameters are uniquely identified.

- $a = \overline{OA}$ the length of half the major axis
- $b = \overline{OB}$ the length of half the minor axis
- $k = \overline{OK}$ the distance from O of a centre on the horizontal axis
- $j = \overline{OJ}$ the distance from O of a centre on the vertical axis

- h the distance of the connecting point H from OB
- m the distance of the connecting point H from OA
- r_1 the length of the radius \overline{AK}
- r_2 the length of the radius \overline{BJ}
- $\beta = \widehat{AKH}$ the angle formed by the line of the centres and the major axis
- $p = \frac{\overline{OB}}{\overline{OA}}$ the ratio of the two axes

For a well-known property J , K and H are on the same line. We assume throughout this paper that $a > b$.

The problem of finding all constructions for any combination of three (independent) parameters is still open. On pag.21 and in the Appendix in (Mazzotti, 2019) these are numbered, and some basic ones are shown (pages 21-39). The ones that interested a number of mathematicians, architects and engineers, because they could solve the practical problem of building a bridge, an arch, an amphitheatre or a dome, are those where the parameters a and b are given. In other words, the problem of inscribing an oval inside a rectangle.

Inscribing an oval inside a rectangle

In this section we are interested in illustrating both geometrical and practical methods of drawing an oval when the semi-axes a and b and a third parameter from the previous list are given. These are cases of "constrained ovals", as discussed in (Mazzotti & Ilchmann, 2023).

Benedetti's constructions

In the recent paper (Hotz & Ilchmann, 2024), the authors illustrate the oval constructions of the Italian mathematician Giovanni Battista Benedetti (1530-1590), who had, already in 1585, solved the problem of inscribing an oval inside a rectangle, having fixed the lengths of either of the two radii.

Fig. 2 Benedetti's first construction of an oval.

We call the first construction B1, as Hotz and Ilchmann do, and illustrate it as follows (Fig. 2):

(B1) Given $\overline{OA} = a$, $\overline{OB} = b$ and $\overline{OJ} = j$ (or equivalently a , b and $r_2 = b + j$) one draws a circle with centre J and radius r_2 and calls P one of its intersections with the perpendicular to OB through J . The other intersection of PA with the previously drawn circle is the connecting point H , since the intersection K of JH with the horizontal axis forms with A and H an isosceles triangle, similar to JPH .

The oval is then drawn by connecting the points H , H' , H'' and H''' - symmetrical to H with respect to the axes and to the origin - by means of circular arcs with centres J , K , J' and K' (see Fig. 1).

For this construction to work, j must verify the condition $j > \frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b}$, which is justified in (Mazzotti, 2019) on p.69.

In the second construction B2 one is supposed to know the half axes a and b and the position of a centre on the horizontal axis (see Fig. 3):

(B2) Given $\overline{OA} = a$, $\overline{OB} = b$ and $\overline{OK} = k$ (or equivalently a , b and $r_1 = a - k$) one finds a point P on OB (on the side of the inscribing rectangle) such that $\overline{BP} = \overline{AK}$ and joins P with K . The perpendicular to PK through its midpoint is then drawn and its intersection J with the vertical axis determined. Let H now be the intersection of JK with the circle with centre K and radius \overline{AK} . Then we have that $\overline{JK} = \overline{JP}$ (since JKP is an isosceles triangle) and $\overline{BP} = \overline{KA} = \overline{KH}$. This in turn implies that $\overline{JB} = \overline{JH}$ and so the arch \widehat{BH} with centre J can be drawn and it shares a tangent with the arc \widehat{AH} with centre K since J , K and H are on the same line.

For this construction to work, k must be such that $a - b < k < a$, otherwise no oval is possible (see (Mazzotti, 2019), inside the proof of Theorem 2.2, on p.11).

Fig. 3 Benedetti's second construction of an oval.

This construction was published in (Bosse, 1665) and (Tosca, 1757), among others, without any reference to Benedetti, and this has led to the erroneous assumption in both cases that *they* might have discovered it. For a list of

Benedetti's legacy concerning his oval constructions, for other constructions of his, involving circles, and for the original text of his letters to P. Pizzamano see (Hotz & Ilchmann, 2024).

Dual versions of Benedetti's constructions

Dual versions of a theorem or formula are often found in mathematics, as long as two interchangeable sets are involved. In the case of ovals, you can simply exchange all the elements belonging to one axis with those belonging to the other axis. We will namely reformulate Benedetti's construction using the following substitutions:

$$a \leftrightarrow b, \quad j \leftrightarrow -k, \quad r_1 \leftrightarrow r_2, \quad A \leftrightarrow B, \quad J \leftrightarrow K, \quad \text{horizontal} \leftrightarrow \text{vertical}$$

j and k are seen here as coordinates, that is why they don't share the same sign. We now formulate (B1d), the dual version of (B1), and check it afterwards:

(B1d) Given $\overline{OB} = b$, $\overline{OA} = a$ and $\overline{OK} = k$ (or equivalently b , a and $r_1 = a - k$) one draws a circle with centre K and radius r_1 and calls P its intersection with the perpendicular to OA through K . The other intersection of PB with the previously drawn circle is the connection point H , since the intersection J of KH with the vertical axis forms with B and H an isosceles triangle, similar to KPH .

Fig. 4 shows that this construction works.

Fig. 4 The dual version of Benedetti's first construction

The dual version of Benedetti's second construction already appeared in (Mazzotti, 2019), (Construction 3a on p.24), where it is called Bosse's (dual) construction, since it is based on what was thought to be Bosse's invention, not Benedetti's.

(B2d) Given $\overline{OB} = b$, $\overline{OA} = a$ and $\overline{OJ} = j$ (or equivalently b , a and $r_2 = b + j$) one finds a point P on OA (on the side of the inscribing rectangle) such that $\overline{AP} = \overline{BJ}$ and joins P with J . The perpendicular to PJ through its midpoint is then drawn and its intersection K with the horizontal axis determined. Let H now be the intersection of KJ with the circle with centre J and radius \overline{BJ} . Then we have that $\overline{KJ} = \overline{KP}$ (since KJP is an isosceles triangle)

and $\overline{AP} = \overline{JB} = \overline{JH}$. This in turn implies that $\overline{KA} = \overline{KH}$ and so the arc \widehat{AH} with centre K can be drawn and it shares a tangent with the arc \widehat{BH} with centre J , since K, J and H are on the same line.

Fig. 5 shows how this dual construction works.

Fig. 5 The dual version of Benedetti's second construction

The Connection Locus

In 1995 Felice Ragazzo (Ragazzo, 1995) identified the set of all points connecting two arcs forming a quarter oval inside a given rectangle. He gave this set the name *Connection Locus* (in Italian: *Luogo dei Raccordi*). Any point on this set can be chosen and the corresponding quarter oval (and then, by symmetry, the whole oval) can be easily drawn. In this way, all the ovals inscribed in the given rectangle can be drawn. A proof via analytic geometry by F. Ghione appears in the cited paper (on p.22). Properties of the Connection Locus have been found and listed in (Mazzotti, 2019) (see Theorem 2.2).

The Connection Locus had already been discovered, and most of its properties proved, in 1897 by the French mathematician Amédée Mannheim. In his work (Mannheim, 1897) he uses it to find the connection point lying on an arbitrary line through the endpoint of the major axis A (see the next section on *Other Constructions*).

The Connection Locus allows for a quarter oval to be drawn. The remaining part of the curve is obtained by reflection w.r.t. the two axes. Follow the construction using Fig. 6.

(CL) Being $OADB$ the rectangle where the quarter oval should be inscribed, draw the axis of the segment AB and intersect it with the bisector of the fourth quadrant. Using the obtained point C as centre one draws a circular arc from A to B . The part of the arc inside $OADB$, excluding its endpoints A and S is the set of all possible connecting points for a quarter oval inscribed in $OADB$ – the *Connection Locus*.

Any choice of a point H on the Connection Locus delivers a quarter oval in a straightforward way: for example, just intersect the axis of \overline{HA} with the horizontal axis to find the centre K and intersect the axis of \overline{HB} with the vertical axis to find the centre J , and so on. On the other hand, the choice of any of the parameters (see introductory section on four-centre ovals) k, j, m, h, r_1, r_2 or a half line through A (see below) - within the range of feasible values - identifies a unique point H on the CL and thus a specific oval. As can be easily proved, the centre C of the *Connection Locus* forms with A and B a right-angled isosceles triangle.

Fig. 6 Constructing the Connection Locus for a quarter oval

Other constructions

An oval inside a given rectangle with a given value β for the angle of the line through two consecutive centres can be constructed via a method attributed to Huygens¹ (see Fig. 7), where it is proved it for the value $\beta = 60^\circ$.

(H) Given $\overline{OA} = a$, $\overline{OB} = b$ and β , to draw the oval with half axis a and b with the line through two consecutive centres forming an angle β with the horizontal axis, start by drawing the line through the origin forming an angle β with the horizontal axis. Call P its intersection with the circle with centre O and radius \overline{OA} , and F the intersection of the latter with the vertical axis. Now draw the segment PF and its parallel through B . The intersection H of this line with the line AP is the connecting point for the searched oval, since the line parallel to OP through H delivers the centres K and J respectively on the x - and on the y -axis.

The triangle JBH is isosceles, because it is similar to FPO , which means that $\overline{JB} = \overline{JH}$ and the arc \widehat{BH} with centre J can be drawn; similarly it can be seen that \widehat{AH} with centre K can be drawn, since KAH is similar to the isosceles triangle OPA .

Another construction given the same three parameters appeared in (Mazzotti, 2019). It is similar to that of Huygens but uses the CL to find point H . It is illustrated in Fig. 8.

(Maz) Given $\overline{OA} = a$, $\overline{OB} = b$ and β , to draw the oval with half axis a and b where the line through two consecutive centres forms an angle β with the horizontal axis, start by drawing the line through the origin forming an angle β with the horizontal axis. Find its intersection E with the circle with centre O and radius \overline{OB} . Let C be the vertex of the right-angled isosceles triangle having AB as hypotenuse. Draw now the CL, with centre C and radius $\overline{CA} = \overline{CB}$. Its intersection H with the line BE is the connecting point for the half oval.

Since the point P in Huygens' construction by Huygens is on the line through H and A , the same construction can be used to find an oval with given axes whose connection lies on a given line through A . This is due to (Mannheim, 1897), who quotes Huygens' construction as being the same one, although for a value of $\widehat{AOP} = \beta = 60^\circ$. The construction is shown in Fig. 9.

¹ No direct reference has yet been found.

Fig. 7 Huygens' construction given a , b and β

Fig. 8 Mazzotti's construction given a , b and β

(Man) Given $\overline{OA} = a$, $\overline{OB} = b$ and a half line originating in A , to draw the half oval with half axis a and b having the connecting point H on this line, find the point P where this line meets the circle with centre O and radius \overline{OA} and F the intersection of the latter with the vertical axis. Now draw the segment PF and its parallel through B . The intersection H of this line with the line AP is the connecting point for the searched oval, and the line parallel to OP through H delivers the centres K and J respectively on the x - and on the y -axis.

Easily derived limit values for $\gamma = \angle \hat{A}P$ are 45° and 90° .

Fig. 11 Inscribing the oval in a rectangle, given a centre on the vertical axis, using nails and a rope

(TE) A peg is fixed at point J (see Fig. 11) and one end of a rope is tied around it. The other end is taken such that the rope is as long as \overline{JB} , free to move. A point K_1 between O and A is now chosen while the rope draws an arc of circle around J until it meets K_1 ; at this point the trajectory of the endpoint of the rope changes, deviating towards the horizontal axis, eventually reaching it. Two arcs of circle sharing a common tangent in H_1 have been drawn by the trajectory of the free endpoint of the rope. Trying out now different positions for K_* one is able to find the point (K_3 in our example), where exactly point A is reached, thus forming the quarter oval AH_3B inside $OADB$.

This method is obviously not as precise as the previous ones, but it can be used onsite, where geometric constructions often have to be made with ropes and pegs anyway. The second cited video also contains the version with a rectangle whose vertical axis is longer than the horizontal.

extra parameter	constraint	set no.	possible methods	Figures
j	$j > \frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b}$	3	(B1) (B2d) (CL) (TE)	2, 5, 6 and 10
k	$a - b < k < a$	1	(B2) (B1d) (CL)	3, 4 and 6
β	$2 \arctan \frac{a}{b} - \frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2}$	23	(H) (Maz)	7 and 8
h	$a - b < h < a$	2	(CL)	6
m	$0 < m < b$	4	(CL)	6
half line with origin A	$\frac{\pi}{4} < \gamma < \frac{\pi}{2}$	-	(CL) (Man)	6 and 9

Table 1 Different construction methods of an oval inscribed in a rectangle (i.e. given a and b) according to the extra given parameter.

General overview

The results of this section are summarised in Table 1.

Given an inscribing rectangle, that is, values for its semi-axes a and b , any additional parameter, within feasible values (these are either straightforward or proved in (Mazzotti, 2019), starting from p. 67), yields a unique oval by means of one of the methods defined above. The set of given parameters is numbered according to the tables on pages 21 and 189 of the cited book.

Borromini's dome in San Carlino

Francesco Castelli, better known as Borromini (1599-1667), worked on the complex of the church of San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane in Rome, also known as San Carlino, between 1634 and 1667. For the impost of the dome (see Fig. 12) he had to find a shape that would fit the space available to him, he was not free to choose any oval shape, such as those with special geometrical features. A proposal for the complex interior decoration, also made of ovals, is described in detail in (Caputo & Mazzotti, 2019) and in its Italian translation (Caputo & Mazzotti, 2025).

Fig. 12 The dome of San Carlino photographed from below (courtesy of Sophie Püschmann, published under permission).

Borromini had to inscribe an oval inside a rectangle measuring 11.79 by 8.05 metres (or actually the values in Roman palms of 52.762 and 36.050, respectively). Of all the possible ovals, he finally chose the one with a centre whose distance from the origin was equal to the major axis. So, his parameters were $a = j = 5.895$ and $b = 4.025$, and according to the condition that $j > \frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b}$, justified in (Caputo & Mazzotti, 2019) on p.69, this is possible.

The three hypotheses

There are three hypotheses as to how this construction was achieved. The Connection Locus (CL), Benedetti's first construction (B1) or the trial-and-error construction with pegs and ropes (TE). These three constructions, applied to the impost of San Carlino, are illustrated in Figs.13, 14 and 15.

In all cases the value $k = 2.3044$ is obtained².

² In the case of the nails and rope method, one can reasonably imagine a slight increase in the value for k , due to the thickness of the rope, amounting to about half of it.

Fig. 13 Inscribing the oval for the impost of the dome in San Carlino using the Connection Locus method (CL)..

Fig. 14 Inscribing the oval for the impost of the dome in San Carlino using Benedetti's first construction (B1).

Fig. 15 Inscribing the oval for the impost of the dome in San Carlino using nails and a rope (TE).

Oval construction(s) actually used

Until 2023 the Connection Locus hypothesis seemed to be the only possible one. In Mazzotti's cited works it was suggested that Borromini might have been able to derive this construction himself, or that it was already known, since a proof of the connection locus theorem for a wider class of polycentric curves was shown in (Mazzotti, 2014a) to be possible simply by using Euclidean geometry. But in (Mazzotti, 2014b) it is also suggested that oval constructions inside a given rectangle, unknown to us today, may have been available in Borromini's time.

Then (Hotz & Ilchmann, 2024) discovered Benedetti's letters, included in (Benedetti, 1585), in which the two constructions of ovals inscribed in a rectangle (B1) and (B2) are presented. It is very likely that Borromini knew Benedetti's work, even though the mathematician died nine years before the architect was born. Borromini, born in today's Switzerland, spent most of his life in Rome. One of the first citations of Benedetti's constructions is that of Christophorus Clavius (1538-1612), a mathematician and Jesuit priest who also lived in Rome, in (Clavius, 1604), and whose pupil Teodosio Rossi, an expert in the measurement of time, was responsible, together with Borromini, for the project of the sundial in the gardens of the Quirinale Palace in Rome in 1628 (Nonaka, 2014). The problem with Benedetti's construction B1 is that in order for Borromini to construct the oval on the building site, he would have had to be able to reach as far as point P in Fig. 13 (or an equivalent point), even further away from the inscribing rectangle than point J . Quite a challenge on such a small building site.

The method using pegs and a rope, on the other hand, was easy to apply, requiring a rope no longer than $r_2 = b + j = 9.92 \text{ m}$ to be fixed at point J and then symmetrically to J' on the other side of the rectangle. A circular arc with centre J (and another one with centre J') was to be constructed on the site anyway.

At this point, it seems plausible that Borromini used Benedetti's first construction B1 when drawing the impost oval on paper and then the "pegs and rope" method on the building site.

As explained in detail in (Lopez Mozo, 2011), the arches forming the vaults inside the *Escorial* in Spain, which were built between 1563 and 1584, before Benedetti's work, had to have a certain span and height: "The existing groin and cloister vaults in the building prove that our masters knew how to reduce the height of an arch without changing the span, in order to correctly solve the intersection of the barrel vaults." (A. Lopez Mozo in the cited article, on p.586). This knowledge, if no other geometric construction is found before Benedetti's, could well have been that of being able to use a trial-and-error method by means of pegs and a rope.

Conclusions

The mathematical and practical knowledge in Borromini's time and after him is the key to understanding how ovals or semi-ovals could be drawn for domes, bridges and arches when span and height or width and length could not be arbitrary. Further study of how architects and engineers worked could confirm the use of precise geometric constructions on paper and practical constructions with pegs and ropes on the building site.

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